

The StuWiss Corpus as a Base for Studying Formulaic Language in Student Academic Writing in L1 and L2 German – Considerations and Challenges in Corpus Design and Annotation

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The StuWiss Corpus as a Base for Studying Formulaic Language in Student Academic Writing in L1 and L2 German – Considerations and Challenges in Corpus Design and Annotation The PhD project presented explores the formulaic lexical resources L1 and L2 students draw on in their academic writing in German. For this, the StuWiss corpus (Studentisches Wissenschaftliches Schreiben – Student Academic Writing) is being built. It currently consists of 208 master theses (4.8 million tokens), submitted to five German as a Foreign Language (GFL) departments at German universities. The collection of a comprehensive metadata set, with information on the master's thesis and the educational and linguistic background of each submittee, allows for the composition of sub corpora, specifically the division of the main corpus into two similarly large L1 and L2 sub corpora. The first goal of the PhD project is to determine the inventory of multi-word units that students possess overall, but also in L1 and L2 comparison. This quantitative (statistical) access via linear and syntactic n-grams is complemented by qualitative (syntactic and functional) analyses of the found multi-word units. These analyses can provide insights into the formal morphosyntactic nature as well as the functional domains and usage specifics of the multi-word units in student academic writing – specifically in L1 and L2 comparison. The paper presented at the LCR Graduate Student Conference will place emphasis on the considerations and challenges of designing, compiling and preparing the StuWiss corpus, from the data collection to the data cleaning to the data annotation, including syntactic dependency annotation, to the evaluation of data quality leading up to the first test runs computing n-grams.

References

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